

Interpretable Factor Models with Machine Learning

Olamide Ayodele¹, Paul Laux²

¹ Institute of Financial Services Analytics, University of Delaware, 591 Collaboration Way, Newark, Delaware, 19713

² Institute of Financial Services Analytics, University of Delaware, 591 Collaboration Way, Newark, Delaware, 19713

Abstract

Understanding the sources of cross-sectional variation in asset returns remains central to financial economics. This paper introduces a *Cluster-Based Factor Model (CBFM)* that integrates hierarchical clustering and locally linear embedding (LLE) to construct parsimonious, data-driven factors from characteristics-managed returns. The clustering stage identifies groups of highly correlated characteristics managed returns, while the subsequent LLE stage extracts low-dimensional nonlinear factors within each cluster. Factor loadings are then estimated through a neural network framework, enabling flexible, time-varying relationships between latent factors and asset returns. Empirical evaluation using Fama–French 25 value-weighted portfolios shows that the CBFM achieves nearly twice the explanatory and predictive R^2 of traditional economic and categorical groupings. Compared with benchmark models such as RP–PCA and standard PCA, the CBFM yields smaller and statistically insignificant alphas, demonstrating superior pricing accuracy and reduced overfitting. These findings highlight the efficacy of data-driven clustering for uncovering the true structure of systematic risk.

Key Words: Factors, Characteristics Managed Returns (CMR), Local Linear Embedding, Hierarchical Clustering

1. Introduction

Understanding why different assets earn different average returns remains one of the most enduring questions in financial economics. Despite decades of research progress, there is still no consensus on the minimal set of systematic factors that can fully explain the cross-sectional variation in expected returns. While early models provided elegant theoretical foundations for linking risk and return, empirical evidence continues to show that returns are influenced by multiple sources of risk that vary across assets and over time. The growing body of evidence on firm-level characteristics—such as size, value, profitability, and momentum—suggests that observable variables contain valuable information about risk exposures. Yet, the rapid expansion of proposed characteristics has led to an overabundance of potential factors, creating uncertainty about which ones truly represent distinct and priced sources of systematic risk. This proliferation underscores the need for models that can synthesize large sets of characteristics into a coherent, interpretable structure without imposing overly restrictive assumptions.

At the same time, purely statistical methods that infer latent factors from return data have proven powerful for dimensionality reduction but often fall short in economic interpretability. Methods such as principal component analysis and its modern extensions can efficiently summarize return covariances, yet the resulting factors are frequently difficult to reconcile with known economic mechanisms. Moreover, most of these approaches assume globally linear relationships between factors and firm characteristics, overlooking local heterogeneity that may arise when assets differ structurally in their sources of risk. For example, assets in different industries, size categories, or growth regimes may share distinct local risk patterns that global factor models fail to capture. As a result, there remains a persistent tension between flexibility and interpretability—between models that fit the data well and those that provide meaningful economic insight.

Our paper addresses this gap by proposing the *Cluster-Based Factor Model (CBFM)*, a hybrid framework that combines clustering and factor modeling to identify both global and local structures of systematic risk. The CBFM partitions characteristics managed returns (CMR) in statistically meaningful clusters based on their correlation score and then extracts latent factors within each cluster to capture dominant within-group variations in returns. This approach allows for heterogeneity in factor formation across different types of assets while preserving the parsimony of the overall factor structure. Conceptually, the model generalizes the idea of characteristic-sorted factors by endogenizing the grouping process, letting the data determine similar risk exposures rather than relying on arbitrary sorting thresholds. Methodologically, it integrates machine-learning techniques—hierarchical clustering and locally linear embedding—with traditional econometric tools for factor estimation, providing a flexible but interpretable framework

for identifying the building blocks of systematic risk.

Empirically, the CBFM is evaluated using a broad panel of CMR. The analysis compares the model’s ability to explain and predict the cross-section of returns relative to established benchmarks, including Fama-French factors, principal component–based models, and deep-learning–driven factor approaches. By examining both explanatory power and pricing errors, the study assesses whether the cluster-based factors capture incremental dimensions of risk beyond those explained by existing models. The results demonstrate that the proposed framework enhances both interpretability and empirical performance, offering a unified approach that bridges the gap between traditional factor-based asset pricing and modern machine-learning methods. In doing so, the CBFM contributes to the ongoing effort to build asset-pricing models that are data-driven yet grounded in clear economic logic.

2. Related Work

Factors play a central role in asset-pricing models, representing systematic sources of risk that help explain the cross-sectional variation in expected returns. The economic rationale is that investors require compensation for bearing pervasive risks that cannot be diversified away. The construction and representation of these factors vary considerably depending on the modeling approach. Broadly, two main paradigms dominate the literature. In one, factors are pre-specified and constructed from observable firm characteristics believed to proxy for underlying sources of risk. The Fama–French three-factor model of Fama and French [11], later expanded to a five-factor model by Fama and French [12], exemplifies this approach by forming portfolio-return factors based on size, value, profitability, and investment characteristics. These models interpret firm-level variables as economically meaningful measures of systematic risk exposures. However, the characteristic-based framework has evolved into what Harvey et al. [19] termed the “factor zoo,” with hundreds of variables proposed as return predictors. Hou et al. [20] documented the limited robustness of many of these characteristics, underscoring the difficulty of identifying truly independent and persistent risk factors. To address this, several recent studies, such as Kozak et al. [25], Fama and French [13], and Feng et al. [15], have developed new methods of factor construction that move beyond traditional portfolio-sorting approaches. These range from rank-based weighting schemes to deep learning architectures designed to construct economically guided factors that minimize pricing errors, offering more flexible yet still interpretable alternatives to conventional models.

The second paradigm treats factors as latent variables, inferred statistically from large panels of returns rather than specified a priori. This tradition builds on the factor-analytic framework pioneered by Connor and Korajczyk [9] and formalized by Bai and Ng [2], Bai [1], and Lam and Yao [26], who established consistent estimation procedures for both the number of factors and their loadings in high-dimensional settings. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) remains the most widely used method under this framework, assuming that a few common shocks explain most of the covariation in returns. Subsequent studies expanded this approach by linking factors to observable firm characteristics. For instance, Kelly et al. [22] proposed Instrumented PCA (IPCA), where characteristics serve as instruments to estimate time-varying factor loadings using an alternating least-squares algorithm. Gu et al. [18] further extended this logic using deep autoencoders to model nonlinear mappings between firm characteristics and latent factors, while Lettau and Pelger [29] and Fan et al. [14] introduced risk-premium and projected PCA variants that improve cross-sectional fit and estimation efficiency. Yet, despite these advances, a persistent challenge remains: many of these latent factors, though statistically powerful, lack economic interpretability. Kozak et al. [24] and Kozak and Nagel [23] emphasize that parsimony and interpretability should remain central objectives, arguing that a small number of dominant factors often suffice to capture the main sources of systematic risk in returns.

Beyond factor construction, an equally important dimension in the literature concerns the estimation of factor loadings—the sensitivities of asset returns to systematic risks. Traditional methods assume static loadings, implying that the relationship between factors and returns remains stable over time. However, empirical evidence suggests that loadings evolve with business-cycle fluctuations, firm characteristics, and market conditions (Stock and Watson [33]; Shanken [32]). This realization has prompted both parametric and non-parametric innovations. Kelly et al. [22] modeled loadings as linear functions of observable characteristics, estimated iteratively through alternating least squares, while Connor et al. [8] and Su and Wang [34] proposed flexible, data-driven frameworks where loadings vary smoothly over time and across assets. More recent work, including Gu et al. [18] and Bakalli et al. [3], integrates machine-learning architectures to capture nonlinear and time-varying risk exposures. These advances align with the growing conditional asset-pricing literature (Ferson and Harvey [16]; Lettau and Ludvigson [28]) and highlight the importance of accounting for dynamic relationships between firm characteristics and systematic risk factors. Building on this literature, the proposed *Cluster-Based Factor Model (CBFM)* aims to integrate the strengths of both research streams—constructing factors from clusters of similar CMR while estimating time-varying loadings that reflect evolving risk exposures—to achieve a flexible yet interpretable framework for explaining the cross-section of asset returns.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Motivation for Clustering

Clustering, though not new to asset-pricing research, provides a systematic framework for organizing high-dimensional data into groups that capture latent structures and sub-features of the original information set. Ludvigson and Ng [30] grouped a large panel of macroeconomic variables into eight categories based on prior economic intuition, arguing that factors estimated from unrestricted panels often lack interpretability. By structuring data into economically coherent blocks, they facilitated the identification and naming of factors derived from each group. Similarly, Greengard et al. [17] applied a modified t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE) approach to reveal fine-grained cluster structures, identifying six distinct groups of assets that correspond closely to known anomalies such as value, momentum, investment, profitability, and volatility. Their findings emphasize how clustering enhances interpretability by aligning statistical patterns with economic meaning. More recently, Jiao et al. [21] demonstrated that models which do not employ clustering tend to over-identify the number of relevant factors, as distinguishing highly correlated characteristic-managed returns becomes increasingly difficult in high dimensions.

Beyond interpretability, clustering offers a pathway to *factor specificity*. Dimensionality-reduction techniques such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), when applied directly to large panels of returns or characteristics-managed portfolios, often produce factors that are global averages of multiple underlying drivers. For instance, applying PCA to characteristics managed returns constructed from value, momentum, investment, and size characteristics typically yields principal components that combine all four sources of variation into a single factor, reducing their individual interpretability. Clustering mitigates this issue by separating characteristic groups and preserving their distinctiveness prior to factor extraction. In doing so, it enhances the granularity and precision of factor construction, enabling factors that are both more interpretable and more economically meaningful. Each cluster captures CMR with similar statistical behavior or economic profiles, resulting in localized factors that better represent specific dimensions of risk exposure. This separation improves predictive utility.

The choice between economic and statistical clustering approaches is also important. Brown and Goetzmann [5], for example, applied k -means clustering to mutual funds based on historical returns and sensitivities to stochastic variables, showing that the resulting groups outperformed traditional style classifications in explaining cross-sectional return variation. While our primary focus is on statistical clustering—which relies purely on the data structure rather than pre-defined economic categories—we also explore the implications of economic clustering as a robustness check. Both methods seek coherence within clusters, ensuring that the resulting groups reflect either shared economic rationale or statistical similarity.

Motivated by the interpretability, specificity, and flexibility of clustering, we adopt clustering as a foundational component of our framework. In the next subsection, we outline the rationale for selecting hierarchical clustering as our clustering algorithm of choice and explain how its structure aligns with the objectives of factor construction in high-dimensional financial data.

3.2 Motivation for Hierarchical Clustering

Hierarchical clustering (HC) offers distinct advantages for constructing latent factors in asset pricing. Unlike partitioning clustering algorithms that require pre-specifying the number of clusters, HC generates a hierarchy of nested partitions, beginning either with singleton clusters and successively merging them (agglomerative) or with one large cluster and recursively splitting it (divisive). We employ the agglomerative approach for computational tractability and interpretability. This data-driven flexibility is particularly useful in settings where the optimal number of clusters—and hence latent factors—is unknown *ex ante*, a challenge emphasized by Jiao et al. [21].

A notable strength of hierarchical clustering is its ability to produce a *dendrogram*, a tree-like diagram that visually represents how clusters merge at varying levels of dissimilarity (Figure 1). In this structure, each leaf node (green dot) represents a characteristics-managed return, and branches indicate how similar assets or portfolios combine into clusters. The vertical height at which two branches merge reflects their degree of dissimilarity, and a horizontal cut determines the final number of clusters. The resulting clusters are both data-driven and interpretable, offering a clear view of the latent structure underlying asset characteristics.

Historically, hierarchical clustering has been widely used in disciplines requiring precise and interpretable groupings, such as biology and genomics, where taxonomies are built to reflect hierarchical relationships among entities. Its robustness, transparency, and ability to reveal multi-level structures make it particularly appealing for financial applications. In the context of factor modeling, hierarchical clustering ensures that the systematic risks captured by each cluster remain relatively independent, aligning with the fundamental assumption of factor orthogonality. By leveraging this approach, we aim to identify clusters that both minimize within-group dissimilarity and preserve between-group

independence, yielding latent factors that are distinct, interpretable, and consistent with the statistical properties of standard factor models.

Figure 1: The green dots at the bottom represent unique characteristics-managed returns, while the ovals highlight the distinct clusters formed. The dashed line denotes the cutoff height determining the optimal number of clusters.

3.3 Methodological Framework for the Cluster-Based Factor Model (CBFM)

3.3.1 Hierarchical Clustering of Characteristics-Managed Returns

This subsection presents our framework on hierarchical clustering characteristics managed returns based on how correlated they are. We denote $\{x_{k,t}\}_{t=1}^T$ as the T -length time series of the k -th characteristics-managed return (CMR), for $k = 1, \dots, N$ characteristics. The stacked characteristics managed returns as $\mathbf{x}_k = (x_{k,1}, \dots, x_{k,T})' \in \mathbb{R}^T$ and $X = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times N}$.

A key input to the hierarchical clustering algorithm is the dissimilarity matrix, which quantifies the pairwise dissimilarity between data points. While distance metrics are widely used as dissimilarity matrix, we derive our dissimilarity matrix based on correlation. We rely on a number of studies that regard correlation as a robust measure of similarity for returns. Also, Lance and Williams [27] posits that if one is interested in interrelationships between attributes rather than their absolute values, the correlation coefficient is appropriate. As a result, we define the dissimilarity between two characteristics-managed returns, \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j as one minus their historical correlation:

$$d(x_i, x_j) = 1 - \rho_{x_i x_j}, \quad D = [d(x_i, x_j)]_{i,j=1}^N. \quad (1)$$

and our dissimilarity matrix of size $N \times N$, with each element $[d(x_i, x_j)]_{i,j=1}^N \in [0, 2]$. The higher the dissimilarity score between two characteristics managed returns, the more uncorrelated they are.

We define the historical correlation as

$$\rho_{x_i x_j} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T (x_{i,t} - \bar{x}_i)(x_{j,t} - \bar{x}_j)}{\sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T (x_{i,t} - \bar{x}_i)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T (x_{j,t} - \bar{x}_j)^2}}, \quad \bar{x}_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T x_{i,t}.$$

Following the dissimilarity matrix, we are next faced with forming clusters, where each of the cluster contains highly correlated or similar characteristics managed returns. We make use of the Agglomerative hierarchical clustering (HC) and Lance–Williams update.

First, we begin with singleton clusters, where each cluster contain single characteristic managed return, i.e $C = \{C_1, \dots, C_N\}$ with $C_k = \{x_k\}$, and then we merge clusters upward until more merging no longer improve the result. During merging, we update our dissimilarity matrix using the Lance-Williams dissimilarity update formula (Lance and Williams [27]);

$$d(C_{i \cup j}, C_k) = \alpha_i d(C_i, C_k) + \alpha_j d(C_j, C_k) + \beta d(C_i, C_j) + \gamma |d(C_i, C_k) - d(C_j, C_k)|, \quad (2)$$

where the two clusters being merged are denoted as C_i and C_j , while C_k represents any other cluster not involved in the merge. The updated distance between the newly formed cluster $C_{i \cup j}$ and C_k is given by $d(C_{i \cup j}, C_k)$, which is calculated using equation 2. The distances between clusters C_i and C_k , as well as between C_j and C_k , are represented by $d(C_i, C_k)$ and $d(C_j, C_k)$, respectively. The distance between the two clusters before merging is $d(C_i, C_j)$. The coefficients α_i , α_j , β , and γ are determined based on choice of linkage method.

We choose the complete linkage method, as it defines the distance between two clusters as the maximum distance between any two characteristics-managed returns variables in different clusters. This method is particularly effective in scenarios where tightly-knit clusters with minimal within-cluster variation are desired. Unlike single linkage, which can result in the chaining effect and produce elongated, loosely connected clusters, complete linkage emphasizes cohesion within groups, ensuring the formation of compact and distinct clusters. This characteristic makes it a natural choice for our research, where an intensive grouping strategy is essential to maintain the integrity and interpretability of the resulting clusters (Lance and Williams [27]). However, our methodology remains flexible and accommodates alternative linkage methods as needed. For a comprehensive review of other linkage methods, we refer the reader to Lance and Williams [27].

For complete linkage, the coefficients $\alpha_i = \frac{1}{2}$, $\alpha_j = \frac{1}{2}$, $\beta = 0$, and $\gamma = -\frac{1}{2}$ in eqn 2, and the Lance–Williams dissimilarity update formula reduces to the maximum distance criterion:

$$d(C_{i \cup j}, C_k) = \max\{d(C_i, C_k), d(C_j, C_k)\}. \quad (3)$$

Algorithm 1 Complete Linkage Hierarchical Clustering

- 1: **procedure** COMPLETE LINKAGE(D) ▷ D is a given dissimilarity matrix
 - 2: **Initialization:** $C \leftarrow \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_N\}$, where each $C_i = \{x_i\}$ is a singleton cluster of distinct characteristic managed return.
 - 3: **while** $|C| > 1$ **do**
 - 4: Find the pair of clusters (C_i, C_j) such that:

$$(C_i, C_j) = \arg \min_{C_i, C_j \in C, C_i \neq C_j} D(x_i, x_j)$$
 - 5: Merge the clusters C_i and C_j to form a new cluster $C_{i \cup j}$
 - 6: Update the dissimilarity matrix by computing $D(C_{i \cup j}, C_k)$ for all remaining clusters $C_k \in C \setminus \{C_i, C_j\}$:

$$D(C_{i \cup j}, C_k) = \max_{x_i \in C_{i \cup j}, x_j \in C_k} D(x_i, x_j)$$
 - 7: Replace C_i and C_j in C with $C_{i \cup j}$
 - 8: **end while**
 - 9: **Output:** The dendrogram representing the hierarchical structure with a cut producing K clusters via elbow or silhouette score
 - 10: **end procedure**
-

The process of forming clusters from the characteristics-managed returns is summarized in Algorithm 1. Starting with characteristics managed returns of dimensions $T \times N$, we first calculate the time-weighted dissimilarity matrix using equation 1. This matrix serves as the input for the complete linkage hierarchical clustering algorithm. Initially, each CMR is treated as a distinct cluster. The algorithm then identifies the pair of CMR with the smallest dissimilarity

(i.e., the pair exhibiting the highest correlation) and merges them into the same cluster. Subsequently, the dissimilarity matrix is updated using the Lance-Williams update rule in equation 2, with the coefficients determined by the complete linkage method.

Choosing the optimal number of clusters, K , is critical in hierarchical clustering, as it affects both interpretability and model robustness. Choosing too few clusters may merge unrelated economic themes, while too many can fragment highly related variables. To determine K , we apply two complementary approaches: the Elbow Method and the Silhouette Method.

The Elbow Method identifies a natural breakpoint, or “elbow,” in the sequence of dissimilarity values from the clustering process, marking where additional clusters provide diminishing improvement in within-cluster homogeneity. If the true number of clusters is K^* , then for any $K < K^*$, the resulting clusters remain subsets of the underlying structure. We detect the elbow by computing the second-order differences of the dissimilarity sequence:

$$\Delta^2 D_i = D_{i+1} - 2D_i + D_{i-1}, \quad (4)$$

and selecting the point where $\Delta^2 D_i$ sharply declines.

To validate cluster quality, we also use the Silhouette Method, which quantifies both intra-cluster compactness and inter-cluster separation. For each characteristic i , the silhouette score is:

$$s(i) = \frac{b(i) - a(i)}{\max\{a(i), b(i)\}}, \quad (5)$$

where $a(i)$ denotes the average dissimilarity of i within its cluster, and $b(i)$ is the minimum average dissimilarity of i to the nearest neighboring cluster. The mean silhouette score for a configuration with K clusters is

$$S(K) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N s(i), \quad (6)$$

with higher values indicating better-defined clusters.

Finally, we distinguish among three clustering modes used in this study: (i) *Statistical Clustering*, employing hierarchical clustering as described above; (ii) *Economic Clustering*, which groups characteristics by economic themes from prior literature; and (iii) *Categorical Clustering*, which classifies variables based on data sources following [6]¹.

3.3.2 Local Linear Embedding

Next, we present the second step of our cluster-based factors: locally Linear Embedding (LLE), a non-linear dimension reduction method. Dimension reduction is crucial as it helps address the problem of high dimensionality, a concern raised by Cochrane [7].

Locally Linear Embedding (LLE), introduced by Roweis and Saul [31], is a non-linear dimensionality reduction technique that focuses on preserving the local geometric structure of data in the embedding space. This fits into our goal as our key objective is to obtain a faithful representation of the clustered data of characteristics managed returns (CMR) in a lower-dimensional space. Faithful representation, in this context, implies that the relationships in the original data are preserved i.e similar characteristics managed returns in high-dimensional space are appropriately weighted in the reduced space. This ensures that factor representations respect the underlying relationships within each cluster. By emphasizing local geometry, LLE captures the most relevant structures that influence assets returns without being overly influenced by global distortions.

Another significant motivation of using LLE is the simplicity in hyperparameter tuning. LLE only requires two hyperparameters: the number of nearest neighbors and the target dimensionality. In our application, one of these parameters—the target dimensionality per cluster—is predefined to be 1 component (factor) per cluster based on the fact that we have clustered highly correlated characteristics managed returns into distinct clusters and expect that one factor should represent all the characteristics in the specific cluster. This leaves only the nearest neighbor parameter to tune, making LLE a computationally efficient and easy-to-implement choice while still flexible. This simplicity ensures consistency and reduces the risk of overfitting or suboptimal performance due to improper parameter settings.

Building on the output of clusters of characteristics managed returns. Suppose there are K optimal clusters from our hierarchical clustering denoted as C_1, C_2, \dots, C_K with each cluster containing n_k CMR grouped together, our factor representation using locally linear embedding proceeds as follow:

¹A full mapping of characteristics and categories is available at www.openassetpricing.com. We also show it in Table 4

Algorithm 2 Dimensionality Reduction with LLE for Clustered Characteristics

Require: K clusters of characteristic-managed returns X , each cluster of dimension $T \times n_k$, where n_k is the number of characteristics in cluster k

Ensure: Reduced dimensional factor f_k of dimension $T \times 1$ in each cluster

- 1: **Step 1: Apply LLE to Each Cluster**
 - 2: **for** each cluster $C_k \subset \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_K\} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times n_k}$ **do**
 - 3: **Step 2a: Compute Nearest Neighbors to each characteristic:**
 - 4: **for** each characteristic $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{C}_k$ **do**
 - 5: Find the j' nearest neighbors of z_t based on Euclidean distance in the N_k -dimensional space.
 - 6: **end for**
 - 7: **Step 2b: Compute Reconstruction weights**
 - 8: **for** each time sample $z_t \in Z_k$ **do**
 - 9: Compute weights w_{ij} that best reconstruct x_i using its j' neighbors:
 Minimize $\sum_{i=1}^{n_k} \left\| \mathbf{x}_i - \sum_{j=1}^{j'} \tilde{w}_{ij} x_{ij} \right\|_2^2$ subject to $\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}(x_i)} \tilde{w}_{ij} = 1$
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: **Step 2c: Compute Low-Dimensional Embedding**
 - 12: Solve the eigenvector problem to minimize the embedding cost:
 Minimize $\sum_{i=1}^{n_k} \left\| y_i - \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}(x_i)} w_{ij} y_j \right\|_2^2$
 - 13: Subject to the constraints:
 $\frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} y_i = 0$
 $\frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} y_i^2 = 1$
 - 14: Obtain the eigenvector corresponding to the second smallest non-zero eigenvalue as the low-dimensional embedding f_k of dimension $T \times 1$.
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: **Step 3: Collect the Factors**
 - 17: Combine the factors $\{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_K\}$, each of dimension $T \times 1$, representing each cluster, into the final set of factors.
 - 18: **Return** the set of reduced dimensional factors $\mathbf{F} = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_K\}$, each of dimension $T \times 1$
-

1. Nearest Neighbors and Reconstruction of Weights:

Fix a cluster C_k with $n_k = |C_k|$ denoting the number of CMR in each cluster and matrix $X_k \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times n_k}$ (columns standardized). Let J be the number of nearest neighbors (NN).

Step 1: NN graph (column-wise). For each column \mathbf{x}_i of X_k , we find CMR whose index set $\mathcal{N}(i) \subset \{1, \dots, n_k\} \setminus \{i\}$ with $|\mathcal{N}(i)| = J$ using Euclidean distance in \mathbb{R}^T .

Step 2: Reconstruction weights. For each CMR i , we form neighbor matrix $X_i = [\mathbf{x}_j]_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times J}$ and compute local covariance

$$G_i = (\mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{1}'_J - X_i)' (\mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{1}'_J - X_i) \in \mathbb{R}^{J \times J}.$$

With a small Tikhonov regularizer $\tau > 0$ ($\tau = 10^{-6}$) to ensure invertibility for near-collinear neighbors, set

$$\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_i = \frac{(G_i + \tau I_J)^{-1} \mathbf{1}_J}{\mathbf{1}'_J (G_i + \tau I_J)^{-1} \mathbf{1}_J} \in \mathbb{R}^J, \quad \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \tilde{w}_{ij} = 1. \quad (7)$$

Assemble the sparse weight matrix $W_{n_k} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_k \times n_k}$ with rows i having nonzeros $(W_{n_k})_{ij} = \tilde{w}_{ij}$ for $j \in \mathcal{N}(i)$ and 0 otherwise.

Step 3: Embedding (eigenproblem). Next, we solve the eigendecomposition problem

$$M_k \mathbf{Y}_k = \mathbf{Y}_k \Lambda_k, \quad \text{where} \quad M_k = (I_{n_k} - W_{n_k})' (I_{n_k} - W_{n_k}), \quad (8)$$

where columns of $\mathbf{Y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_k \times p_k}$ are the eigenvectors associated with the p_k smallest nontrivial eigenvalues Λ_k (the trivial eigenvector $\mathbf{1}$ with eigenvalue 0 is discarded). For our factor construction, we set $p_k = 1$ (one factor per cluster). Let $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_k}$ be that eigenvector (normalized to $\|\mathbf{y}_k\|_2 = 1$).

Step 4: Cluster factor time series. Finally, we project the CMR panel in cluster k onto the embedding weights to obtain a $T \times 1$ factor:

$$\mathbf{f}_k = X_k \mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^T. \quad (9)$$

Collect $\mathbf{F} = [\mathbf{f}_1, \dots, \mathbf{f}_K] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times K}$.

3.3.3 Factor Loadings Estimation

We modify the assumption that asset returns $\mathbf{R}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$ follow a K -factor structure in a linear form to a non linear structure :

$$\mathbf{R}_t = G(\alpha_{t-1}, \beta'_{t-1} \mathbf{f}_t) + \varepsilon_t, \quad \mathbb{E}_t[\varepsilon_t] = 0, \quad \mathbb{E}_t[\varepsilon_t \mathbf{f}'_t] = 0. \quad (10)$$

Here, $\mathbf{f}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times 1}$ are the latent factors constructed via hierarchical clustering and locally linear embedding (Algorithms 1 and 2); β_{t-1} represents time-varying factor loadings, and α_{t-1} captures pricing errors. When $\alpha_{t-1} = 0$, \mathbf{f}_t spans all systematic risk in the cross-section of returns.

We first estimate β_{t-1} non-linearly using a feedforward neural network that maps latent factors \mathbf{f}_t to predicted returns \mathbf{R}_t . The recursive transformation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}^{(0)} &= \mathbf{f}_t, \\ \mathbf{h}^{(l)} &= \sigma(\mathbf{B}^{(l)} \mathbf{h}^{(l-1)} + \alpha^{(l)}), \quad l = 1, \dots, L-1, \\ \widehat{\mathbf{R}}_t &= \mathbf{B}^{(L)} \mathbf{h}^{(L-1)} + \alpha^{(L)}, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{B}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times n_{l-1}}$ and $\alpha^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l}$ denote layer weights and biases, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is an activation function (ReLU or tanh). The output weights $\mathbf{B}^{(L)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times K}$ represent estimated factor loadings β_{t-1} , while $\alpha^{(L)}$ represents idiosyncratic intercepts.

Figure 2: Neural-network architecture for estimating time-varying loadings. The input layer contains K latent factors; two hidden layers with n_1 and n_2 neurons capture non-linear interactions; the output layer produces N predicted returns.

The full mapping from latent factors to predicted returns is:

$$\mathbf{R}_t = \mathbf{B}^{(L)} \sigma \left(\mathbf{B}^{(L-1)} \dots \sigma \left(\mathbf{B}^{(1)} \mathbf{f}_t + \boldsymbol{\alpha}^{(1)} \right) + \dots + \boldsymbol{\alpha}^{(L-1)} \right) + \boldsymbol{\alpha}^{(L)}. \quad (12)$$

This setup allows non-linear and time-varying dependence between returns and latent factors, improving flexibility relative to linear regression models.

In summary, we estimate factor loadings using non-linear conditioning on latent factors \mathbf{f}_t which enhances the explanatory power of our cluster-based factor model (CBFM) relative to linear alternatives.

4. Data and Results

4.1 Data description

We make use of characteristics managed portfolio returns provided by Chen and Zimmermann [6]². We exclude characteristics managed returns with missing values during our sample period, which spans from January 1964 to December 2023 so as not to have imbalanced panel of CMR. This approach eliminates the need for imputation and allows us to focus on 130 out of the 212 characteristics originally provided in the dataset. The choice of this sample period is driven by data availability, as comprehensive accounting information is sparsely recorded before 1964, and because key developments in asset pricing research emerged around that time. The selected characteristics are continuous firm-specific attributes classified into six financial categories: Price, Trading, Accounting, Event, 13F and other, as defined by Chen and Zimmermann [6]. Following Brandt et al. [4] and DeMiguel et al. [10], each predictor is standardized to have a cross-sectional mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. Table 4 in the Appendix lists these characteristics along with their respective financial and economic classifications, as specified by Chen and Zimmermann [6]. Each characteristic is associated with managed portfolio returns, constructed based on the methodologies outlined in the original research papers³.

4.2 Factors from Cluster Results

In this section, we now present some of our findings of our cluster-based factor when applied to 130 characteristics-managed returns. First, we distinguish between clusters that are based on economic intuition, statistical correlation, and category of the characteristics. The 130 characteristics we focus on in this work are economically grouped into 27 themes, which are valuation, accruals, investment, leverage, risk, other, liquidity, profitability, profitability alt, sales growth, investment alt, investment growth, external financing, payout indicator, volume, lead lag, earnings growth, info proxy, momentum, volatility, long term reversal, asset composition, R&D, short sale constraints, short-term reversal, size, and cash flow risk. We take each of these themes as a cluster, which implies that the first stage—hierarchical clustering of our cluster-based factor—is skipped. We also treat the source of the characteristics as clusters, in what we term the categorical clustering. Categorically, our characteristics are grouped into 6 themes, which are Accounting, Price, Trading, Event, Other, and 13F.

Statistically, we cluster CMR based on hierarchical clustering highlighted in earlier section. First, hierarchical clustering groups the CMR into several buckets such that CMR in each bucket are highly correlated. We address the question of how many clusters the CMR should be grouped into. To determine the optimal number of clusters, we use the elbow method and the Silhouette score. Figure 3 plots the difference score, the first-order difference, and the second-order difference as the number of clusters increases. We identify the point where the drop in the difference score becomes negligible for an increasing number of clusters and consider the largest drop in the second-order difference. Both criteria suggest an optimal number of clusters at $K = 3$.

To verify the robustness of this clustering choice, we calculate the average Silhouette score (Table 1) for all characteristics within each cluster. With Silhouette score range from -1 to 1, where a high value indicates that characteristic is well matched to its own cluster and poorly matched to neighboring clusters, we find that the optimal silhouette score of 0.79 occur at $K = 3$. This combination of methods—difference scores and Silhouette scores—provides a strong justification for selecting three clusters for our statistical clustering.

Having established our findings of 3 clusters as the optimal number, we visualize how the characteristics are grouped using the dendrogram in Figure 4⁴. The dashed red horizontal line represents a cut-off height implicitly defined by the optimal clusters identified using the Silhouette score and Elbow method. We observe that cluster 1 primarily includes variables associated with financial leverage and capital structure, such as Net Debt to Price and CAPM Beta.

²We extend our gratitude to Chen and Zimmermann [6] for making their dataset publicly available at <https://www.openassetpricing.com/data/>

³See Chen and Zimmermann [6] for references to the original papers that documented each characteristic.

⁴A clearer version of Fig 4 on how CMR cluster is in Fig 6

Figure 3: Elbow method illustrating the relationship between the number of clusters (K) and the difference. The "elbow point" indicates the optimal number of clusters, beyond which adding more clusters results in minimal improvement

Number of Clusters (K)	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Silhouette Scores	0.42	0.79	0.60	0.52	0.5	0.36	0.48	0.15	0.18

Table 1: The silhouette scores for different numbers of clusters needed for grouping N characteristics managed returns. The optimal number of clusters, $K = 3$, has the largest silhouette score that maximizes $S(K)$ in equation 6.

Cluster 2 captures momentum and earnings-related themes, with characteristics such as 12-Month Momentum and Earnings Streak Length. Finally, cluster 3, the most diverse group, encompasses factors like Size, Book-to-Market, and Asset Growth, representing firm valuation and investment activities.

Next, we apply the locally linear embedding to each of the three clusters. Constructing the factors using LLE requires us to tune the nearest neighbors of each CMR in each cluster. Technically, the number of components needed to reduce the dimensionality is also a hyperparameter. However, given our prior understanding that each cluster contains highly correlated characteristics, we conclude that each cluster will be dimensionally reduced to one factor. For choosing the best number of nearest neighbors for each CMR in each cluster, we perform a grid search over a range of neighbors from 5 to 50. Figure 5 plots the reconstruction error for cluster 1 as it varies with the increasing number of neighbors required for the reconstruction matrix. We find that the optimal number of neighbors that minimizes the reconstruction error for cluster 1 is 20. Similarly, the grid search is performed for clusters 2 and 3, and we determine their respective optimal nearest neighbors by analyzing their reconstruction error plots.

This process ensures that the local geometry of each cluster is well-preserved while reducing the dimensionality to a single representative factor per cluster. The resulting factors encapsulate the most critical structures of the clustered CMR, providing a robust basis for further analyses.

4.3 Empirical Result and Discussion

We evaluate the performance of our Cluster-Based Factor Model (CBFM) by comparing three clustering schemes for constructing factors from characteristics-managed returns: (i) *Statistical Clustering*, which applies hierarchical clustering followed by Locally Linear Embedding (LLE); (ii) *Economic Clustering*, which groups characteristics into 27 economic themes; and (iii) *Categorical Clustering*, which categorizes 130 characteristics into 6 groups by data source.

The optimal number of statistical clusters determined by the hierarchical algorithm is three. For each clustering

Figure 4: Dendrogram visualizing how individual characteristics managed returns cluster at the leaf node, and the branches show sequence of merges, where these characteristics are combined at different levels of dissimilarity. The dashed red horizontal line represents a cut-off height implicitly defined by optimal clusters identified by Silhouette and Elbow method

Figure 5: Reconstruction error for Cluster One as a function of the number of nearest neighbors used in the Reconstruction Matrix for low-dimensional embedding. The grid search identifies the optimal number of neighbors, where the lowest reconstruction error occurs at 20 neighbors for each of the characteristics managed returns in Cluster One.

method, we apply LLE within clusters to extract K reduced components, and we estimate time-varying factor loadings using the neural-network framework described in Section 2. The Fama–French 25 value-weighted portfolios serve as the test assets.

We report two performance metrics: (i) the total R^2 , representing the fraction of *return variance* explained by the factor model,

$$R_{\text{Total}}^2 = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (R_t - F_t \beta_{t-1})^2}{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T R_t^2}, \quad (13)$$

and (ii) the predictive R^2 , which measures the fraction of *realized return variation* explained by the model,

$$R_{\text{Pred}}^2 = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (R_t - F_t \hat{\lambda})^2}{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T R_t^2}. \quad (14)$$

	K (Number of Factors per Cluster)				
	1	2	3	4	5
Panel A: Statistical Clusters (3)					
Total R^2	27.50	26.61	26.61	24.04	22.32
Pred. R^2	5.12	4.88	4.69	4.11	3.82
Panel B: Economic Clusters (27)					
Total R^2	13.00	14.20	14.60	13.10	13.00
Pred. R^2	1.53	1.56	1.56	1.28	1.22
Panel C: Category Clusters (6)					
Total R^2	13.38	13.25	12.90	12.00	12.20
Pred. R^2	1.62	1.57	1.43	1.40	1.41

Table 2: Total and predictive R^2 (in percent) for the Cluster-Based Factor Model using Fama–French 25 portfolios as test assets. Panels A–C correspond to statistical, economic, and categorical clusterings of characteristics-managed returns.

Table 2 shows that the *statistical clustering* approach outperforms both economic and categorical groupings. With $K = 1$ factor per cluster (three total factors), the model attains a total R^2 of 27.5%, doubles the explanatory power of the economic (13.0%) and categorical (13.4%) clusters. Even as K (number of factors per cluster) increases, statistical clustering maintains superior explanatory power across all specifications.

The predictive R^2 results follow a similar pattern: for $K = 1$, statistical clustering achieves 5.12%, compared with 1.53% (economic) and 1.62% (categorical). Although predictive R^2 declines slightly with additional components, the statistical clusters consistently dominate, indicating that the CBFM captures a larger share of both contemporaneous and forward-looking return variation.

This superiority arises from the data-driven nature of statistical clustering, which groups CMR by empirical correlations rather than predefined themes. Consequently, the extracted factors align more closely with true common risks and yield higher explanatory and predictive accuracy than factors derived from ex ante economic or categorical classifications.

4.3.1 Comparison with Alternative Models

Table 3 compares the performance of the Cluster-Based Factor Model (CBFM) with three benchmarks: the Risk-Premium PCA (RP-PCA) of Lettau and Pelger [29], standard PCA [33], and an Observable Factor Model based on CAPM and Fama–French factors. The RP-PCA introduces a penalty parameter γ on average factor returns; we set $\gamma = 50$, following the authors’ specification.

In the CBFM (Panel A), explanatory power declines moderately as the number of factors per cluster increases: total R^2 falls from 27.5% (one factor per cluster) to 22.3% (five factors), and predictive R^2 decreases from 5.12% to 3.82%. Despite this decline, the model achieves low pricing errors, with α values between 0.01 and 0.08 and t -statistics below 2.0 for all but the $K = 5$ case—indicating that the zero-alpha hypothesis cannot be rejected for most specifications. This suggests that the CBFM captures systematic risk efficiently without overfitting.

No. of Factors (K)	1	2	3	4	5
Panel A: Cluster-Based (3 Clusters)					
Total R^2	27.5	26.61	26.61	24.04	22.32
Pred. R^2	5.12	4.88	4.69	4.11	3.82
α	0.01	0.08	0.08	0.01	0.07
t -stats	1.84	1.88	1.89	1.72	2.14
Panel B: RP-PCA ($\gamma = 50$)					
Total R^2	28.75	45.87	48.79	56.20	58.50
Pred. R^2	5.46	9.21	12.58	16.11	16.50
α	0.25	0.23	0.29	0.42	0.16
t -stats	6.66	4.93	4.84	5.12	5.68
Panel C: PCA					
Total R^2	28.02	46.07	52.22	54.10	56.12
Pred. R^2	5.40	8.89	13.20	16.34	16.80
α	0.31	0.24	0.23	0.11	0.09
t -stats	6.43	6.57	6.26	5.46	5.38
Panel D: Observable Factors					
Total R^2	74.10	—	91.38	—	91.97
Pred. R^2	24.91	—	53.00	—	63.13
α	1.07	—	1.21	—	0.85
t -stats	2.77	—	4.60	—	3.12

Table 3: Total and predictive R^2 (in percent) for the Fama–French 25 portfolios under the Cluster-Based Factor Model, RP-PCA [29], standard PCA [33], and observable factor models. K denotes the number of factors used to explain cross-sectional returns.

The RP-PCA (Panel B) and PCA (Panel C) methods yield higher R^2 values as K (number of factors) increases—up to 58.5% and 56.1%, respectively—but at the cost of substantial pricing errors. Both models produce large and statistically significant alphas (t -statistics between 4.8 and 6.7), indicating poor pricing of the assets and a rejection of the zero-alpha hypothesis. The observable-factor benchmark (Panel D) attains the highest total R^2 (up to 91.97%) and predictive R^2 (63.13%) but also shows large pricing errors ($\alpha \approx 1\%$), suggesting that its apparent fit may capture noise rather than true risk premia.

Overall, while RP-PCA and PCA exhibit stronger fit, the CBFM achieves superior pricing accuracy with smaller alphas and insignificant t -values. This balance of explanatory power, parsimony, and pricing precision highlights the CBFM’s effectiveness in modeling systematic risk without introducing excess noise or overfitting.

5. Conclusion and Future Research

This study introduced and evaluated a Cluster-Based Factor Model (CBFM) for constructing and estimating latent factors in asset pricing. The proposed model integrates hierarchical clustering and locally linear embedding (LLE) to identify statistically coherent groups of characteristics-managed returns, followed by a neural-network-based estimation of time-varying factor loadings. This design enhances interpretability and flexibility, addressing long-standing challenges in balancing parsimony, explanatory power, and pricing accuracy in factor modeling.

Empirical evaluation using the Fama–French 25 value-weighted portfolios demonstrates that the CBFM substantially outperforms models based on predefined economic or categorical groupings. Statistical clustering—driven purely by correlation structures—achieves nearly twice the explanatory and predictive R^2 of economic and categorical clusters, confirming that data-driven methods more effectively uncover latent sources of systematic risk. Compared

with benchmark approaches such as Risk-Premium PCA (RP-PCA) [29] and standard PCA [33], the CBFM delivers competitive explanatory power with markedly smaller and statistically insignificant alphas, thereby satisfying the zero-alpha condition and avoiding the overfitting common in traditional statistical methods.

Performance remains robust across alternative factor dimensionalities: while total R^2 declines modestly as more factors are introduced per cluster, the predictive R^2 remains stable, reflecting consistent out-of-sample performance. These results suggest that latent factors derived from hierarchical clustering capture essential common variation in returns while maintaining interpretability and parsimony.

Future Directions. Future research will focus on examining the composition of characteristics-managed returns within each identified cluster to interpret which characteristics dominate and to provide economic meaning to the resulting factors. Since each latent factor is a weighted composition of characteristics-managed returns—which themselves are functions of firm characteristics—interpretability naturally follows from studying this composition. Further work will also extend factor-loading estimation by conditioning directly on asset characteristics, enabling a comparison between characteristic-based and latent-factor conditioning. Additional directions include applying the CBFM to broader test assets such as international equities, industry portfolios, and multi-asset datasets to assess cross-market robustness, and incorporating macroeconomic or regime-dependent variables to capture time-varying risk structures. Finally, integrating advanced machine learning architectures—such as autoencoders or transformers—may further refine non-linear representations of factor exposures within the cluster-based framework.

In conclusion, clustering provides a statistically rigorous and economically meaningful approach to organizing the factor space in high-dimensional asset pricing. By combining hierarchical structure, non-linear dimensionality reduction, and adaptive loadings, the CBFM bridges traditional econometric models and modern machine-learning techniques, offering a robust, interpretable, and data-driven framework for modeling systematic risk.

References

- [1] Bai, J. (2003). Inferential theory for factor models of large dimensions. *Econometrica*, 71(1):135–171.
- [2] Bai, J. and Ng, S. (2002). Determining the number of factors in approximate factor models. *Econometrica*, 70(1):191–221.
- [3] Bakalli, G., Guerrier, S., and Scaillet, O. (2023). A penalized two-pass regression to predict stock returns with time-varying risk premia. *Journal of Econometrics*, 237(2):105375.
- [4] Brandt, M. W., Santa-Clara, P., and Valkanov, R. (2009). Parametric portfolio policies: Exploiting characteristics in the cross-section of equity returns. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 22(9):3411–3447.
- [5] Brown, S. J. and Goetzmann, W. N. (1997). Mutual fund styles. *Journal of financial Economics*, 43(3):373–399.
- [6] Chen, A. Y. and Zimmermann, T. (2021). Open source cross-sectional asset pricing. *Critical Finance Review*, *Forthcoming*.
- [7] Cochrane, J. H. (2011). Presidential address: Discount rates. *The Journal of finance*, 66(4):1047–1108.
- [8] Connor, G., Hagmann, M., and Linton, O. (2012). Efficient semiparametric estimation of the fama–french model and extensions. *Econometrica*, 80(2):713–754.
- [9] Connor, G. and Korajczyk, R. A. (1986). Performance measurement with the arbitrage pricing theory: A new framework for analysis. *Journal of financial economics*, 15(3):373–394.
- [10] DeMiguel, V., Martin-Utrera, A., Nogales, F. J., and Uppal, R. (2020). A transaction-cost perspective on the multitude of firm characteristics. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 33(5):2180–2222.
- [11] Fama, E. F. and French, K. R. (1993). Common risk factors in the returns on stocks and bonds. *Journal of financial economics*, 33(1):3–56.
- [12] Fama, E. F. and French, K. R. (2015). A five-factor asset pricing model. *Journal of financial economics*, 116(1):1–22.
- [13] Fama, E. F. and French, K. R. (2020). Comparing cross-section and time-series factor models. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 33(5):1891–1926.

- [14] Fan, J., Liao, Y., and Wang, W. (2016). Projected principal component analysis in factor models. *Annals of statistics*, 44(1):219.
- [15] Feng, G., He, J., Polson, N. G., and Xu, J. (2024). Deep learning in characteristics-sorted factor models. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 59(7):3001–3036.
- [16] Ferson, W. E. and Harvey, C. R. (1999). Conditioning variables and the cross section of stock returns. *The Journal of Finance*, 54(4):1325–1360.
- [17] Greengard, P., Liu, Y., Steinerberger, S., and Tsyvinski, A. (2020). Factor clustering with t-sne. Available at SSRN 3696027.
- [18] Gu, S., Kelly, B., and Xiu, D. (2021). Autoencoder asset pricing models. *Journal of Econometrics*, 222(1):429–450.
- [19] Harvey, C. R., Liu, Y., and Zhu, H. (2016). . . . and the cross-section of expected returns. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 29(1):5–68.
- [20] Hou, K., Xue, C., and Zhang, L. (2020). Replicating anomalies. *The Review of financial studies*, 33(5):2019–2133.
- [21] Jiao, Y., Zhou, G., and Zhu, Y. (2023). Interpretable factors of firm characteristics. Available at SSRN.
- [22] Kelly, B. T., Pruitt, S., and Su, Y. (2019). Characteristics are covariances: A unified model of risk and return. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 134(3):501–524.
- [23] Kozak, S. and Nagel, S. (2023). When do cross-sectional asset pricing factors span the stochastic discount factor? Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- [24] Kozak, S., Nagel, S., and Santosh, S. (2018). Interpreting factor models. *The Journal of Finance*, 73(3):1183–1223.
- [25] Kozak, S., Nagel, S., and Santosh, S. (2020). Shrinking the cross-section. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 135(2):271–292.
- [26] Lam, C. and Yao, Q. (2012). Factor modeling for high-dimensional time series: inference for the number of factors. *The Annals of Statistics*, pages 694–726.
- [27] Lance, G. N. and Williams, W. T. (1967). A general theory of classificatory sorting strategies: 1. hierarchical systems. *The computer journal*, 9(4):373–380.
- [28] Lettau, M. and Ludvigson, S. (2001). Resurrecting the (c) capm: A cross-sectional test when risk premia are time-varying. *Journal of political economy*, 109(6):1238–1287.
- [29] Lettau, M. and Pelger, M. (2020). Factors that fit the time series and cross-section of stock returns. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 33(5):2274–2325.
- [30] Ludvigson, S. C. and Ng, S. (2009). A factor analysis of bond risk premia. Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- [31] Roweis, S. T. and Saul, L. K. (2000). Nonlinear dimensionality reduction by locally linear embedding. *science*, 290(5500):2323–2326.
- [32] Shanken, J. (1990). Intertemporal asset pricing: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Econometrics*, 45(1-2):99–120.
- [33] Stock, J. H. and Watson, M. W. (2002). Forecasting using principal components from a large number of predictors. *Journal of the American statistical association*, 97(460):1167–1179.
- [34] Su, L. and Wang, X. (2017). On time-varying factor models: Estimation and testing. *Journal of Econometrics*, 198(1):84–101.

Appendix

Data: Characteristics composition

Table 4: Characteristics, Data Categories and Economic Categories

Acronym	LongDescription	Category	Economic
AM1	Total assets to market	Accounting	valuation
Acc2	Accruals	Accounting	accruals
Ass3	Asset growth	Accounting	investment
BM4	Book to market, original (Stattman 1980)	Accounting	valuation
BMd5	Book to market using December ME	Accounting	valuation
BPE6	Leverage component of BM	Accounting	leverage
Bet7	Tail risk beta	Price	risk
Bet8	CAPM beta	Price	risk
Bet9	Frazzini-Pedersen Beta	Price	other
Bid10	Bid-ask spread	Trading	liquidity
Boo11	Book leverage (annual)	Accounting	leverage
CBO12	Cash-based operating profitability	Accounting	profitability
CF13	Cash flow to market	Accounting	valuation
Cas14	Cash Productivity	Accounting	profitability alt
ChA15	Change in Asset Turnover	Accounting	sales growth
ChE16	Growth in book equity	Accounting	investment
ChI17	Inventory Growth	Accounting	investment alt
ChI18	Change in capital inv (ind adj)	Accounting	investment growth
ChN19	Change in Net Noncurrent Op Assets	Accounting	investment alt
ChN20	Change in Net Working Capital	Accounting	investment alt
ChT21	Change in Taxes	Accounting	other
Com22	Composite equity issuance	Accounting	external financing
Com23	Composite debt issuance	Accounting	external financing
Con24	Convertible debt indicator	Accounting	external financing
Cos25	Coskewness using daily returns	Price	risk
Cos26	Coskewness	Price	risk
Del27	Change in current operating assets	Accounting	investment alt
Del28	Change in current operating liabilities	Accounting	external financing
Del29	Change in equity to assets	Accounting	investment
Del30	Change in financial liabilities	Accounting	external financing
Del31	Change in long-term investment	Accounting	investment
Del32	Change in net financial assets	Accounting	investment alt
Div33	Dividend Initiation	Event	payout indicator
Div34	Dividend seasonality	Event	payout indicator
Div35	Predicted div yield next month	Accounting	valuation
Dol36	Past trading volume	Trading	volume
EBM37	Enterprise component of BM	Accounting	valuation
EP38	Earnings-to-Price Ratio	Accounting	valuation
Ear39	Earnings consistency	Accounting	earnings growth
Ear40	Earnings Surprise	Accounting	earnings growth
Ear41	Earnings surprise of big firms	Accounting	lead lag
Ent42	Enterprise Multiple	Accounting	valuation
Equ43	Equity Duration	Accounting	valuation
Exc44	Exchange Switch	Event	other
Fir45	Firm age based on CRSP	Other	info proxy

Continued on next page

Acronym	LongDescription	Category	Economic
Fro46	Efficient frontier index	Accounting	valuation
GP47	gross profits / total assets	Accounting	profitability
GrL48	Growth in long term operating assets	Accounting	investment
GrS49	Sales growth over inventory growth	Accounting	sales growth
GrS50	Sales growth over overhead growth	Accounting	sales growth
Her51	Industry concentration (sales)	Other	other
Her52	Industry concentration (equity)	Other	other
Her53	Industry concentration (assets)	Other	other
Hig54	52 week high	Price	momentum
Idi55	Idiosyncratic risk (3 factor)	Price	volatility
Idi56	Idiosyncratic risk (AHT)	Price	volatility
Ill57	Amihud's illiquidity	Trading	liquidity
Ind58	Industry Momentum	Price	momentum
Ind59	Industry return of big firms	Price	lead lag
Int60	Intangible return using CFtoP	Accounting	long term reversal
Int61	Intangible return using EP	Accounting	long term reversal
Int62	Intangible return using Sale2P	Accounting	long term reversal
Int63	Intermediate Momentum	Price	momentum
Inv64	Investment to revenue	Accounting	investment
Inv65	change in ppe and inv/assets	Accounting	investment
Inv66	Inventory Growth	Accounting	profitability
LRr67	Long-run reversal	Price	long term reversal
Lev68	Market leverage	Accounting	leverage
MRr69	Medium-run reversal	Price	long term reversal
Max70	Maximum return over month	Price	volatility
Mea71	Revenue Growth Rank	Accounting	sales growth
Mom72	Momentum (12 month)	Price	momentum
Mom73	Momentum without the seasonal part	Price	other
Mom74	Momentum (6 month)	Price	momentum
Mom75	Off season long-term reversal	Price	other
Mom76	Off season reversal years 6 to 10	Price	other
Mom77	Off season reversal years 16 to 20	Price	other
Mom78	Momentum and LT Reversal	Price	momentum
Mom79	Return seasonality years 2 to 5	Price	other
Mom80	Return seasonality years 6 to 10	Price	other
Mom81	Return seasonality years 11 to 15	Price	other
Mom82	Return seasonality years 16 to 20	Price	other
Mom83	Return seasonality last year	Price	other
Mom84	Momentum in high volume stocks	Price	momentum
Mom85	Off season reversal years 11 to 15	Price	other
NOA86	Net Operating Assets	Accounting	asset composition
Net87	Net debt to price	Accounting	leverage
Net88	Net Payout Yield	Accounting	valuation
Num89	Earnings streak length	Accounting	earnings growth
OPL90	Operating leverage	Accounting	other
Ope91	Operating profits / book equity	Accounting	profitability
Ope92	Operating profitability R&D adjusted	Accounting	profitability
Org93	Organizational capital	Accounting	R&D
Pay94	Payout Yield	Accounting	valuation
Pri95	Price	Price	other

Continued on next page

Acronym	LongDescription	Category	Economic
RD96	R&D over market cap	Accounting	R&D
RDA97	R&D ability	Accounting	other
RIO98	Inst Own and Market to Book	13F	short sale constraints
RIO99	Inst Own and Turnover	13F	short sale constraints
RIO100	Inst Own and Idio Vol	13F	short sale constraints
Rea101	Realized (Total) Volatility	Price	volatility
Res102	Momentum based on FF3 residuals	Price	momentum
Ret103	Return skewness	Price	risk
Ret104	Idiosyncratic skewness (3F model)	Price	risk
Rev105	Revenue Surprise	Accounting	sales growth
RoE106	net income / book equity	Accounting	profitability
SP107	Sales-to-price	Accounting	valuation
STr108	Short term reversal	Price	short-term reversal
Sha109	Share issuance (1 year)	Accounting	external financing
Sha110	Share issuance (5 year)	Accounting	external financing
Sha111	Share Volume	Trading	volume
Siz112	Size	Price	size
Spi113	Spinoffs	Event	other
Sur114	Unexpected R&D increase	Accounting	R&D
Tax115	Taxable income to income	Accounting	other
Tot116	Total accruals	Accounting	investment alt
Tre117	Trend Factor	Price	momentum
Var118	Cash-flow to price variance	Accounting	cash flow risk
Vol119	Volume Variance	Trading	liquidity
Vol120	Volume to market equity	Trading	volume
Vol121	Volume Trend	Trading	volume
dNo122	Change in net operating assets	Accounting	investment
grc123	Change in capex (two years)	Accounting	investment growth
grc124	Change in capex (three years)	Accounting	investment growth
sin125	Sin Stock (selection criteria)	Other	other
std126	Share turnover volatility	Trading	liquidity
tan127	Tangibility	Accounting	asset composition
zer128	Days with zero trades	Trading	liquidity
zer129	Days with zero trades	Trading	liquidity
zer130	Days with zero trades	Trading	liquidity

Clusters of Characteristics

